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BALTIC+ Theme 3 Baltic+ SEAL (Sea Level)

Validation Report

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LIST OF ACRONYMS

VR: Validation Report

ATBD: Algorithm Theoretical Basis Document

TG: Tide Gauge

DAC: Dynamic Atmosphere Correction

NAP: Normal Amsterdams Peil (Reference Frame)

RMSE: Root Mean Square Error

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1 INTRODUCTION

This document holds the Validation Report (VR) prepared by Baltic+ SEAL team, as part of the activities included in the WP3 of the Proposal. The documents present a summary of the statics produced to validate different stages of the algorithm development. In particular, Section 2 summarises the results of the validation concerning the classification of the radar echoes in order to distinguish ice from open water; while Section 3 lists the main findings and statistics based on the comparison of the along-track raw high-rate dataset of sea level anomalies for each mission considered in this project against tide gauge data. In the next version of this document, the multi-mission gridded dataset will be validated.

2 VALIDATION OF THE CLASSIFICATION STRATEGY

The along-track open-water detection results of the unsupervised classification are compared with spatio-temporally matching optical and radar images, in order to evaluate the classification performance and reliability. Therefore, the classification results are overlain by image data, which are close in time (max. 1h) and show a good overlap to the altimetry overflights. The comparison of all included missions, except Envisat and SARAL/AltiKa, which were validated in (Müller, Dettmering, Bosch, & Seitz, 2017), is conducted in the Bay of Bothnia due to seasonal ice coverage and the development of narrow leads. The unsupervised classification algorithm follows for all missions the same strategy and processing tools, which are explained in (Müller, Dettmering, Bosch, & Seitz, 2017) and the Algorithm Theoretical Basis Document (ATBD) of Baltic+ SEAL.

Following section shows visual comparisons of the various altimetry missions underlining the good performance of the individual classifications. The comparisons are summarised in a table for each mission. Due to a better readability and general view not all comparisons are visualized in the Validation Report. Grey highlighted comparisons can be found in the Appendix.

The reliability of comparison is dependent on the sea-ice drift. Therefore, the acquisition time gap (in minutes) is provided for each overlap. The algebraic sign describes the chronological order of the record. If it's positive the altimetry overflight was before the image acquisition and vice versa.

In case of optical images, near black areas correspond to water openings within the sea-ice. Reddish regions indicate land topography and bluish as well as greyish different sea-ice types. Analysing (side-looking) radar images, lead areas appear as very thin elongated black areas, due to a very specular behaviour of smooth and calm surfaces. Moreover, an enhanced surface roughness leads to a brighter, more greyish grey level. However, very thin ice surfaces, like Nila (i.e. smooth surface) ice, with a thickness up to 5cm lead to appear very dark. Furthermore, open ocean areas are mostly featured by high grey-scale values, due to stronger wave movements. Due to this ambiguities, radar images are not in every case the best option for validating classification results.

ESA European Remote Sensing satellite 2 (ERS-2) and ESA Environmental Satellite (Envisat)

The radar altimeter RA-1 is mounted on the ERS-2 satellite platform and shows similar behaviour with its successor ESA mission Envisat carrying an improved radar altimeter version, RA-2. The classification of RA-1 waveforms follow the strategy of Envisat waveform, which were quantitatively validated by using 16 SAR images of CSA mission Radarsat-2 and JAXA ALOS in (Müller, Dettmering, Bosch, & Seitz, 2017), showing an overall performance of about 71% true detection rate. The validation is based on 15000 Envisat observations in the Greenland Sea.

Due to fixed, adverse revisit times of ERS-2 and potential comparison missions, the comparison suffers from a sparse availability of overlaps in the northern Baltic region. Only optical images from Landsat mission 5 and 7 are suited to give an impression of the good detection rates of the ERS-2 open-water classification. The comparisons are labelled by a caption code, which are summarized in following Table.

Table 1 Comparison pairs - ERS-2

Caption	Validation Mission	Date
ERS-2_C1	Landsat-7	2001-04-22
ERS-2_C2	Landsat-7	2001-04-22
ERS-2_C3	Landsat-7	2002-03-06
ERS-2_C4	Landsat-7	2003-04-17
ERS-2_C5	Landsat-5	1997-03-25
ERS-2_C6	Landsat-7	2000-04-08

Comparison: ERS-2_C1

Comparison: ERS-2_C2

Comparisons ERS-2_C1 and ERS-2_C2 show a very nice classification performance. The classification algorithm identifies smallest leads up to several meters and can detect ice returns originating from different sea-ice types (floes, Nila ice). At the top of ERS-2_C1 fast ice areas, producing ocean like returns, are reliable assigned to ice areas.

CNES/NASA Jason-1, Jason-2, Jason-3

Since the CNES/NASA missions Jason-1, Jason-2 and Jason-3 are characterized by very similar instrumental features and orbit characteristics, the classification of radar waveforms of all three missions is based by using Jason-2 radar echoes as a reference. Moreover, the extended mission parts (e.g. geodetic mission phases) are treated equally.

Table 2 Comparison pairs - Jason-1, Jason-2, Jason-3

Caption	Validation Mission	Date
J1_C1	Landsat-5	2006-04-28
J1_C2	Landsat-5	2011-02-28
J2_C3	Sentinel-1A	2015-01-16
J2_C4	Sentinel-1A	2015-01-20
J2_C5	Sentinel-1A	2015-01-23
J2_C6	Sentinel-1A	2015-02-04
J2_C7	Landsat-8	2016-04-14
J2_C8	Landsat-8	2016-04-14
J2_C9	Sentinel-1A	2015-03-19
J2_C10	Landsat-8	2016-04-21
J2_C11	Sentinel-1A	2015-03-19
J2_C12	Sentinel-1A	2015-03-28
J2_C13	Sentinel-1A	2015-03-30
J2_C14	Sentinel-1A	2016-01-06
J2_C15	Sentinel-1A	2016-01-13
J2_C16	Sentinel-1A	2016-01-23
J2_C17	Sentinel-1A	2016-03-08
J2_C18	Sentinel-1A	2016-03-12
J2_C19	Sentinel-1A	2016-03-22
J2_C20	Sentinel-1A	2016-03-29
J2_C21	Sentinel-1B	2017-01-06
J2_C22	Landsat-8	2017-04-08
J2_C23	Sentinel-1B	2017-02-27
J2_C24	Sentinel-1B	2017-03-09
J2_C25	Sentinel-1B	2017-04-17
J2_C26	Sentinel-1B	2017-04-24
J3_C27	Sentinel-1A	2016-03-08
J3_C28	Sentinel-2A	2018-03-23
J3_C29	Landsat-8	2016-04-14
J3_C30	Landsat-8	2016-04-14
J3_C31	Sentinel-1A	2016-03-22
J3_C32	Landsat-8	2016-04-21
J3_C33	Sentinel-1A	2016-03-29
J3_C34	Sentinel-2A	2018-03-30
J3_C35	Landsat-8	2017-03-30
J3_C36	Sentinel-2A	2019-03-22
J3_C37	Sentinel-2A	2019-03-22
J3_C38	Sentinel-2B	2018-03-08
J3_C39	Landsat-8	2017-04-17
J3_C40	Sentinel-2B	2018-03-15
J3_C41	Landsat-8	2018-03-19
J3_C42	Landsat-8	2019-03-26
J3_C43	Landsat-7	2018-03-27
J3_C44	Sentinel-2B	2019-03-07
J3_C45	Landsat-8	2018-04-02
J3_C46	Sentinel-1B	2017-03-11
J3_C47	Landsat-7	2019-03-07
J3_C48	Landsat-8	2019-03-22
J3_C49	Sentinel-1B	2017-04-26
J3_C50	Sentinel-1B	2017-04-29
J3_C51	Sentinel-1B	2018-02-13
J3_C52	Sentinel-1B	2018-02-17
J3_C53	Sentinel-1B	2018-02-27
J3_C54	Sentinel-1B	2018-03-02
J3_C55	Sentinel-1B	2018-03-04
J3_C56	Sentinel-1B	2018-04-07
J3_C57	Sentinel-1B	2018-04-21
J3_C58	Sentinel-1B	2018-04-26

Comparison: J2_C7

Comparison: J2_C19

Comparison: J3_C29

The comparison for the CNES/NASA missions using one reference model, show for all three missions the same results. Comparison J2_C19 and J3_C31 as well as J2_C7 and J3_29 are based on the same background radar/optical image. Jason-2 and Jason-3 are in tandem phase operation, just separated 2 minutes from each other. The number of water detections is nearly identical. However, some a few open water returns are registered by Jason-2. Explanations might be a changed situation due to drifting sea-ice or slight instrumental changes resulting in a differing waveform

characteristics between both missions. Comparisons J3_C36 and J3_40 display different sea-ice situations, with a satisfying classification performance.

CNES/ISRO SARAL/AltiKa

The unsupervised classification of 40Hz SARAL/AltiKa observations was validated in the Greenland Sea following the descriptions of (Müller, Dettmering, Bosch, & Seitz, 2017). The validation is based on nearly 20000 altimetry observations and 19 radar images as comparison dataset and yields a consistency rate of about 77%. The classification strategy is directly transferable without any modifications to the Baltic Sea. Therefore, the same detection performance can be assumed and expected.

Copernicus/ESA Sentinel-3A/B

The unsupervised classification strategy is also adapted to Delay-Doppler waveforms of Copernicus ESA satellites Sentinel-3A/B. However, most of the comparison are referred to Sentinel-3A, due to the currently short mission time of Sentinel-3B with launch in April-2018.

Table 3 Comparison pairs Sentinel-3A/B

Caption	Validation Mission	Date
S3A_C1	Landsat-8	2017-03-16
S3A_C2	Sentinel-2A	2018-04-09
S3A_C3	Landsat-7	2017-03-31
S3A_C4	Landsat-7	2017-03-31
S3A_C5	Landsat-8	2017-04-08
S3A_C6	Landsat-8	2017-04-08
S3A_C7	Landsat-8	2018-02-22
S3A_C8	Landsat-8	2018-02-22
S3A_C9	Sentinel-2B	2018-04-17
S3A_C10	Sentinel-2B	2018-04-17
S3A_C11	Sentinel-2B	2018-04-17
S3A_C12	Sentinel-2B	2019-03-03
S3A_C13	Landsat-7	2019-03-30
S3A_C14	Sentinel-2B	2019-03-03
S3A_C15	Landsat-8	2019-04-07
S3A_C16	Landsat-7	2019-04-22
S3A_C17	Sentinel-2B	2019-03-03
S3A_C18	Sentinel-2B	2019-03-07
S3A_C19	Sentinel-2B	2019-03-30
S3B_C20	Landsat-7	2019-02-26
S3B_C21	Sentinel-2A	2019-03-25
S3B_C22	Landsat-7	2019-04-13
S3B_C23	Sentinel-2A	2019-04-17
S3B_C24	Sentinel-2A	2019-04-17
S3B_C25	Sentinel-2B	2019-04-09

Comparison: S3A_C7

Comparison: S3A_C9

Slight changes in the feature space are required for adapting the unsupervised classification approach to Delay-Doppler waveforms. In general, the classification results of Sentinel-3A/B are convincing. Sea-ice floes or rough sea-ice surfaces are detected and flagged (e.g. S3A-C9, S3B_C21). However, an unexpected behaviour of the absolute backscatter coefficients with respect to thin ice can be observed. Comparison S3A_C7 shows areas with a very thin refreezing sea-ice layer resulting in a water-ice mixture, which produces very strong backscatter coefficients. The values are even higher than the backscatter from leads, which leads to miss-classifications and additional water detections. Figure 1 shows an ice chart from 2018-02-22 indicating different ice-types. Nila-ice as well as new-ice regions are illustrated in light green up to yellow. Nearly all observations within these parts are assigned to water detections. Moreover, Delay-Doppler observations of Cryosat-2 are not affected in the same way, like returning radar echoes from Sentinel-3A/B. One explanation might be a changed handling of the incoming waveforms and backscatter treatment or the adjustment of the Automatic Gain Control in connection with the generation of Multi-Look waveforms of Sentinel-3A/B. Nevertheless, the nila-ice and new-ice layer are very thin (i.e. several centimetres) and radar echoes from these surface can be seen as reflected by the water level.

Figure 1 Cryosat-2 overflight with classification results and sea-ice chart from 2018-02-22, displaying different ice types. Nila-ice in light green; new-ice in yellow; fast-ice in black, hummocked ice in dark green and closed ice with leads in green (©FMI, (Berglund & Eriksson, 2015))

ESA Cryosat-2

The unsupervised classification approach is also applied to CryoSat-2 Delay-Doppler waveform data.

Table 4 Comparison pairs CryoSat-2

Caption	Validation Mission	Date
CS2_C1	Sentinel-1A	2016-03-16
CS2_C2	Sentinel-1A	2016-03-20
CS2_C3	Sentinel-1A	2016-04-10
CS2_C4	Sentinel-2A	2019-03-22
CS2_C5	Sentinel-1A	2016-04-10
CS2_C6	Sentinel-1B	2018-02-18
CS2_C7	Sentinel-1B	2018-02-20
CS2_C8	Sentinel-1B	2018-02-28
CS2_C9	Sentinel-1B	2018-03-02
CS2_C10	Sentinel-1B	2018-03-16
CS2_C11	Sentinel-1B	2018-03-19
CS2_C12	Sentinel-1B	2018-03-21
CS2_C13	Sentinel-1B	2018-03-28
CS2_C14	Sentinel-1B	2018-04-16

The Cryosat-2 classification results show very good performance, which is confirmed by Dettmering et al. 2018. The unsupervised classification, using 25 clusters, was independently validated by high-resolved optical images from NASA Operation Ice Bridge resulting in an overall classification accuracy of 97%, which can be directly transferred to the

Baltic Sea region. Very small leads are detected (CS2_7). However, roughed ice areas, characterized by small ice and snow-covered hummocks are tending to ocean-like radar shapes, which are falsely assigned to ocean conditions. The problem can be solved by introducing external sea-ice charts labelling hummocked ice areas to the process.

3 VALIDATION OF THE ALONG-TRACK DATASET

For a complete description of the collection and processing of the tide gauge (TG) data, the reader is referred to the Dataset Description report of this project (D2.1). The following sections and figures are to be considered as a resume of the full set of figures (over a hundred, consisting of all the TG-Altimetry coupling for every along-track mission), which can be made available under request.

3.1 Methods

The TG and altimeter sea level measurements are not equivalent and hence both data sets were further processed before they were compared. The altimeter data sets are corrected for atmospheric pressure effect using Dynamic Atmosphere Correction (DAC). As applying the DAC to the TG data would further complicate the comparison, the altimetry data was decorrected by adding the DAC back to the sea level height before the comparison, as done previously, for example, by Ruiz Etcheverry et al. (2015). The TG sea level data was also detrended. Detrending removes the effect of land uplift, prominent especially in the northern Baltic Sea, in the TG data.

In order to validate the new altimeter data sets, the nearest altimeter track points to TGs were calculated for each cycle 3-10 km away from the tide gauges and 3-10 km away from the coast, using the distance to coast parameter in the altimeter data set. Additional distances to coast can be chosen for comparison. The 3-km limit is the typical limit of confidence that is assigned to ALES+ data according to previous studies (Passaro et al., 2018). As TGs are located on the coastlines, the performance of the altimeter data set was explored in the vicinity of the shoreline, allowing testing of the limits of the altimeter product in the complex Baltic archipelagos. Furthermore, the sea-ice-index parameter was used to exclude altimeter track points other than open water. The TG data has high temporal resolution (at least one hour) which allowed the interpolation of the EVRF2007 heights to the time of the altimeter overpass with one minute accuracy (similarly to Birol and Delebecque, 2014).

There is a clear difference in sea level reference frame as the altimeter sea level height is tied to the TOPEX geoid, and TG sea level height data to Normaal Amsterdams Peil (NAP) reference frame. Hence the altimeter sea level was brought to the EVRF2007 level by setting the time-average from the altimeter data equal to the TG time-average for each TG and altimetry mission separately. This allowed for visual inspection of the time series variability but inhibits the comparison of means. During visual inspection, some clear errors and spikes in the altimeter data were observed, and hence the altimeter data was filtered using the measured maximum and minimum values from the TG data, calculated over the whole measurement period. With the thresholds applied, the values crossing the TG maximum and minimum values were removed from the altimeter data and flagged as bad data. After the filtering process, the levelling was performed from the beginning excluding the data that was previously flagged as bad. While this strategy cannot be adopted for the final gridded product, it provides a way to analyse the quality of the coastal data excluding the outliers. Once the gridded dataset is computed, this procedure should not be necessary anymore, since outliers would have been already excluded during the gridding process.

The root mean square error (RMSE), Pearson correlation (r) and number (n) of along-track data points used in the comparison were computed for all TGs and altimetry missions. As the statistics would not be representative for $n < 20$, those results were left out of the validation. For Sentinel-3A, both ALES+ and SAMOSA2 retrackerers were applied. As the Sentinel-3B mission started only in 2018, there was not enough data points to include it in the validation. Also Jason-1GM and Jason-2 EM were left out, as there were only three TGs with $n > 20$.

3.2. Validation results

We have chosen eight TGs (Figure 1) with large number of data points so that the statistics is based on larger dataset and different altimetry missions can be compared for the same TGs. Only some TGs are situated within 3-10 km distance from altimeter tracks, which limits the spatial coverage of validation points. The selected TGs are Bagenkop, Ballen, Daugavgriva, Kalix, Kaskinen, Kemi, Mäntyluoto (close to Pori, Finland) and Rodvig. The best validation results are obtained from SARAL/AltiKa mission, where RMSE is under 12 cm and r is over 0.80 for six tide gauges. The least successful results are for Jason-3, where for four TGs RMSE is over 20 cm and r is under 0.80. Overall, Mäntyluoto (six missions) has best results (RMSE under 12 cm and r over 0.85 excepting ERS-2).

In order to further interpret the results, some considerations are necessary on the locations of the tide gauges. Kalix and Kemi are representative of conditions in which sea ice plays a major role during winter, i.e. the Bothnian Bay. Therefore, the validation of along-track data is mostly restricted to the sea-ice-free season. Ballen, Rodvig and Bagenkop are located in the Danish Straits, which besides being an important area for water exchange between the Baltic and the North Sea, it is extremely challenging for coastal altimetry due to the presence of multiple land-ocean transitions and islands. Kaskinen and Mäntyluoto, in the eastern coast of Finland, are also located in bays where several islets are present, while Daugavgriva is located at the estuary of the river Daugava in the Gulf of Riga.

Scatter plots and time series for five different tide gauges and missions are shown. In the scatter plots, the fitted linear curve is shown with correlation and the number of points. The scatter plot of Cryosat-2 at Kemi (Fig.2) has $r = 0.88$ and the time series plot (Fig.3) shows that the extremes are captured quite well in the altimeter data 2010-2018. For Jason-

1, there are 229 data points at Mäntyluoto (Fig.4, $r=0.91$) and the time series 2002-2009 (Fig.5) exhibits good correspondence between altimeter and TG data. At Kalix, there are 215 data points in Jason-2 data with $r = 0.87$ (Fig. 6). The time series 2008-2016 (Fig.7) shows that the extremes are moderately approximated in the altimeter data. Daugavgriva is situated at coast of the Gulf of Riga. Correlation in the scatter plot of SARAL/AltiKa mission is high (Fig.8, $r=0.97$) and altimeter and TG time series are close to each other (Fig.9). The differences in Sentinel-3A data between ALES+ and SAMOSA2 retracers are very small. When outliers are excluded from the data, the numbers of data points differ between retracers for some TGs. In Kalix, $n < 20$ for SAMOSA2, and only statistics for ALES+ is shown in Table 13. This shows that in this location ALES+ is able to retrack more valid points than SAMOSA2, which is promising given that the area is affected by sea ice in the winter season. Even if the Sentinel-3A (ALES+) data has only few points at Rodvig ($n=29$), the correlation is high (Fig.10, $r=0.95$) and altimeter and TG time series are quite similar (Fig.11). Tables 5-13 show the statistical validation results for these TGs and 9 missions.

An attempt to validate Topex data, which are provided in the internal dataset of the project despite the fact that the waveforms cannot be retracked, was performed at Ballen (RMSE = 52 cm, $r = 0.13$, $n = 310$) and at Kemi. For Kemi there were enough points ($n = 56$, 95 outliers) but there was no significant correlation and the RMSE was 91 cm. Results are therefore substantially worse than in all other missions considered in the project.

The following conclusions can be drawn by this analysis:

- 1) A careful outliers analysis is unavoidable if coastal altimetry data have to be applied for sea level analysis at high rate. In the validation exercise, this has been performed based on the tide gauge data. In the application of the along-track dataset and in the post-processing for the gridding, an outliers analysis need to be performed using the fitting error on the waveform and comparing the single estimations with the average variability (using for example as a reference the standard deviation of all the sea level anomalies within a 1-Hz block)
- 2) The ALES+ SAR dataset shows performances that are at least comparable to SAMOSA2 and allows a larger number of valid points to be retrieved in zones affected by seasonal sea ice. This is encouraging and allows to apply the ALES+ SAR retracking with confidence for Cryosat-2 data as well.
- 3) Among the Ku-Band LRM missions, Envisat performs best. This was already noticed for ALES data and it is likely due to the better performances of the on-board tracker compared to the Jason series, which allows more valid waveforms to be retrieved in the transitions between land and ocean. Moreover Envisat had a smaller footprint than the Jason satellites, due to the different orbit altitude
- 4) ERS-2 can be successfully retracked in the coastal zone, despite the fact that its waveforms are noisier, because they are formed by averaging half of the individual echoes used for the same procedure in the other LRM altimeters. This justifies the consideration of the ERS-2 mission for the multi-mission gridded dataset in output of this project and allows to analyse the sea level in the Baltic area starting from May 1995
- 5) An inclusion of TOPEX data in the production of the gridded dataset of this project is not recommended also from the point of view of the performances against tide gauges
- 6) The reason of the worse performances of Jason-3 compared to Jason-2 and Jason-1 is unclear. One possibility is that Jason-3 benefits from a better on-board tracking system that allows more waveforms to be retrieved in the proximity of land. These waveforms nevertheless might be in some cases highly corrupted and therefore not correctly retracked

Future steps planned in this validation are:

- The provision of case-studies where different distances to coast are considered
- The consideration of different tide models to correct altimetry data (tide gauges in the Baltic Sea are not corrected for tides, since the basin is usually considered to be "a-tidal")
- The use of an outlier detection that is independent from the tide gauge

Figure 2. The selected tide gauges.

Table 5. Cryosat -2

Tide gauge	RMSE	r	n
Bagenkop	0.14	0.82	42
Ballen	0.16	0.77	46
Daugavgriva	0.12	0.88	25
Kaskinen	0.12	0.92	33
Kemi	0.17	0.88	39
Mantyluoto	0.11	0.95	27
Rodvig	0.14	0.86	65

Table 6. Envisat

Tide gauge	RMSE	r	n
Bagenkop	0.10	0.84	29
Ballen	0.14	0.71	63
Daugavgriva	0.13	0.83	41
Kaskinen	0.08	0.92	73
Kemi	0.09	0.95	50
Mantyluoto	0.11	0.90	74
Rodvig	0.11	0.81	62

Table 7. ERS-2

Tide gauge	RMSE	r	n
Ballen	0.15	0.76	72
Kemi	0.16	0.81	41
Mantyluoto	0.18	0.75	57
Rodvig	0.10	0.93	63

Table 8. Jason-1

Tide gauge	RMSE	r	n
Ballen	0.15	0.76	203
Daugavgriva	0.25	0.67	97
Kaskinen	0.26	0.53	189
Kalix-Storon	0.10	0.88	81
Kemi	0.26	0.61	41
Mantyluoto	0.10	0.91	229

Table 9. Jason-1_EM

Station	RMSE	r	n
Ballen	0.18	0.76	64
Kemi	0.28	0.75	70
Kalix-Storon	0.11	0.92	52

Table 10. Jason-2

Station	RMSE	r	n
Bagenkop	0.15	0.73	46
Ballen	0.26	0.42	253
Daugavgriva	0.16	0.82	226
Kalix-Storon	0.14	0.87	215
Kaskinen	0.13	0.84	235
Kemi	0.31	0.69	130
Mantyluoto	0.11	0.87	254

Table 11. Jason-3

Station	RMSE	r	n
Bagenkop	0.14	0.81	44
Ballen	0.23	0.58	95
Daugavgriva	0.31	0.69	54
Kalix-Storon	0.14	0.88	78
Kaskinen	0.40	0.40	72
Kemi	0.39	0.56	56

Table 12. SARAL/AltiKa

Station	RMSE	r	n
Bagenkop	0.36	0.55	29
Ballen	0.11	0.84	29
Daugavgriva	0.07	0.97	31
Kaskinen	0.06	0.96	31
Kemi	0.06	0.98	26
Mantyluoto	0.09	0.94	27
Rodvig	0.11	0.85	23

Table 13. Sentinel-3A

Station	RMSE	r	n	SAMOS2	ALES+
Bagenkop	0.05	0.95	27	x	
Bagenkop	0.05	0.95	28		x
Kalix-Storon	0.18	0.71	23		x
Rodvig	0.07	0.94	29	x	
Rodvig	0.07	0.95	29		x

Figure 2. Scatter plot Kemi Cryosat-2

Figure 3. Time series Kemi Cryosat-2

Figure 4. Scatter plot Mäntyluoto Jason-1

Figure 5. Time series Mäntyluoto Jason-1

Figure 6. Scatter plot Kalix Jason-2

Figure 7. Time series Kalix Jason-2

Figure 8. Scatter plot Daugavgriva SARAL/AltiKa

Figure 9. Time series Daugavgriva SARAL/AltiKa

Figure 10. Scatter plot Rodvig Sentinel-3A ALES+

Figure 11. Time series Rodvig Sentinel-3A ALES+

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